

Preregistration: Moderated Latent Variables Mediation Using Correct and Misspecified Models

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Preregistration: Moderated Latent Variables Mediation Using Correct and Misspecified Models

This preregistration follows the ADEMP framework ([Morris et al., 2019](#)) and the template by Siepe et al. ([2024](#)).

General Information

What is the title of the project?

Answer: Moderated Latent Variables Mediation Using Correct and Misspecified Models.

Note that this title may change in the future.

Who are the current and future project contributors?

Answer: Felipe Fontana Vieira and Yves Rosseel

Provide a description of the project.

Answer: A Monte Carlo simulation study comparing three latent variable estimators under a moderated mediation model. The main focus is the index of moderated mediation (imm) as well as the interaction/moderation effect. However, we will also calculate the performance of the other structural parameters and measurement loadings. As we will highlight later on, the misspecifications in principle should affect each differently. We assess how estimation and inference degrade under structural and measurement misspecification and under non-normal exogenous variables.

Did any of the contributors already conduct related simulation studies on this specific question?

Answer: No prior simulation on this specific question, but the authors conducted a simulation study looking at a different model where non-normality of the latent variables involved in the product terms was manipulated (see: https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/xk8um_v3). For this specific project, only preliminary calibration runs were used to fix the misspecification coefficients and to hold reliability and the coefficient of determination (R^2) constant across conditions. We have created a separate document that explains this calibration step-by-step, and will be available on the GitHub repository. Note that this did not involve any estimation, it was simply focused on ensuring that the data generation was valid.

Moreover, the first author did run three times the simulation run for all conditions with 10 replications to ensure no coding issues. For purposes of clarification, this happened because in the

initial case the data generation failed once, then in a second try the results were not correctly stored. This never entailed making any preliminary comparisons, summary calculations, and decisions based on the estimators performance.

Aims

What is the aim of the simulation study?

Answer: Estimation and hypothesis testing. We quantify primarily bias, root mean squared error (RMSE), 95% confidence interval (CI) coverage, standard error (SE) accuracy, Type I error ($a_3 = 0$) and power for the imm and the structural paths, and how these are affected by structural/measurement misspecification and non-normality.

Data-Generating Mechanism

How will the parameters for the data-generating mechanism (DGM) be specified?

Answer: Parametric population structural model:

$$M = a_1X + a_2W + a_3 X:W + \varepsilon_M$$

$$Y = b M + c' X + \varepsilon_Y$$

with $a_1 = 0.4$, $a_2 = 0.3$, $b = 0.5$, $c' = 0.15$ (small-to-medium structural effects, with X and W on a standardized scale) and $\text{cor}(X, W) = \rho = 0.3$. The disturbances $\varepsilon_M, \varepsilon_Y$ are Gaussian and independent of each other and of (X, W) , so non-normality enters M and Y only through the exogenous variables.

The structural residual variances are not free parameters: they are fixed at $\psi_M = 0.8531$ and $\psi_Y = 0.9350$, the values that make each structural equation explain a fraction $R^2 = 0.30$ of its outcome's variance at the central interaction level $a_3 = 0.2$ under the normal baseline (a recognizable medium signal-to-noise level). Fixing them once, rather than re-solving per condition, lets R^2 move only through the design factors: under normality R_M^2 runs $0.274 \rightarrow 0.300 \rightarrow 0.368$ as a_3 goes $0 \rightarrow 0.2 \rightarrow 0.4$.

Each latent variable has four indicators with loadings 1/0.8/0.7/0.6. The indicator error standard deviations are set analytically so that each indicator's reliability hits its target (0.5 or 0.7).

Non-normal exogenous data are generated with the VITA (vine-to-anything) algorithm ([Grønneberg et al., 2022](#)), which builds the joint distribution of (X, W) from a vine copula ([Nagler & Vatter, 2025](#)). This lets us impose genuinely non-normal joint distributions (i.e., non-normal

copulas) while holding the correlation ρ and the standardized margins (mean 0, variance 1) fixed, so distributional shape is varied independently of location, scale, and dependence strength.

Figure 1 depicts this population model. The grey elements are the misspecifications introduced as a design factor (detailed below).

Figure 1

Population Model for the Simulation Study.

What will be the different factors of the data-generating mechanism?

Answer: Sample size, interaction strength (the latent interaction coefficient a_3), reliability, exogenous distribution, and model misspecification. Hence, five in total.

If possible, provide specific factor values for the DGM as well as additional simulation settings.

Answer:

- **Sample size** $\in \{100, 200, 300, 500\}$
- **Interaction strength** (a_3) $\in \{0, 0.20, 0.40\}$

- **Reliability** \in {low = 0.5, high = 0.7} (per-indicator reliability target)
- **Exogenous distribution** \in {normal, uniform, t with 5 degrees of freedom, and two chi-squared shapes that differ only in the sign of the $X-W$ dependence}, each standardized to mean 0 and variance 1, so that only distributional shape varies
- **Misspecification** \in {none; an omitted $W \rightarrow Y$ path; an omitted $X \cdot W \rightarrow Y$ path; a cross-loading of one mediator indicator on X ; and a residual covariance between one mediator and one outcome indicator}, each at a small (0.25) and a medium (0.50) magnitude (9 levels in total; the misspecification design follows Brandt et al. (2020), within the moderated-mediation framework of Preacher et al. (2007))

Held constant: the structural coefficients, $\rho = 0.3$, the loadings, and the 20,000 Monte Carlo draws used for the imm confidence interval. Misspecification magnitudes are calibrated per cell so that reliability and R^2 stay at their no-misspecification values. The estimated model is always the correctly-specified one.

If there is more than one factor: how will the factor levels be combined and how many simulation conditions will this create?

Answer: Fully factorial: $4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 5 \times 9 = 1080$ conditions.

Estimands and Targets

What will be the estimands and/or targets of the simulation study?

Answer:

- Primary: $\text{imm} = a_3b$.
- Secondary: the structural paths (a_1, a_2, a_3, b, c') and the 12 free measurement loadings.

Methods

How many and which methods will be included and which quantities will be extracted?

Answer:

Three estimators of the same latent interaction model:

- **Local structural-after-measurement (SAM)** (Rosseel et al., 2025; Rosseel & Loh, 2024), via the {lavaan} package (Rosseel, 2012). The two interacting exogenous factors share one measurement block, and the mediator and outcome each form their own block.
- **Latent moderated structural equations (LMS)** (Klein & Moosbrugger, 2000), via the {modsem} package (Slupphaug et al., 2024), with robust standard errors.
- **Double mean-centering with product indicators (UPI)**, via the {modsem} package, with robust (maximum-likelihood, MLR) estimation.

For each fitted model we extract the parameter estimates and their covariance matrix. The confidence interval for the imm uses 20,000 Monte Carlo draws (a quantile interval). All other parameters use Wald confidence intervals. We also record admissibility flags (any negative residual variance, or a non-positive-definite latent covariance matrix), applied identically across methods. Otherwise the software defaults are used.

Performance Measures

Which performance measures will be used?

Answer: The measures are those provided by the {simhelpers} package (Joshi & Pustejovsky, 2025), each (where applicable) with a Monte Carlo standard error (MCSE), plus median-based analogues as a robustness check against outlying replications and heavy tails (following the supplemental tables of our earlier simulation study highlighted above). For the interaction effect and the imm, the rejection rate gives the Type I error rate when $a_3 = 0$ and power when $a_3 = 0.2$, computed as 1 minus the coverage of zero (the confidence interval excludes 0). Where the true value is 0, the relative measures are undefined and we report their absolute counterparts.

Performance measure	Empirical calculation	MCSE
Mean-based		
Bias	$\bar{B} - \beta$	$\sqrt{S_B^2/K}$
Relative bias	$\bar{B}/\beta - 1$	$\sqrt{S_B^2/(K\beta^2)}$
RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K (B_k - \beta)^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{K-1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K (\text{RMSE}_{(j)} - \text{RMSE})^2}$
Relative RMSE	$\sqrt{[(\bar{B} - \beta)^2 + S_B^2]/\beta^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{K-1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K (\text{rRMSE}_{(j)} - \text{rRMSE})^2}$
SE/SD ratio	\overline{SE}/S_B	—
Relative bias of variance estimator	$(\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \widehat{SE}_k^2) / S_B^2$	$\sqrt{\frac{K-1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K (\bar{v}_{(j)}/S_{B,(j)}^2 - \text{relVarBias})^2}$
Coverage	$c = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K I(L_k \leq \beta \leq U_k)$	$\sqrt{c(1-c)/K}$
Average width	$\bar{U} - \bar{L}$	$\sqrt{S_W^2/K}$
Rejection rate (Type I / power)	$r = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K I(0 \notin [L_k, U_k])$	$\sqrt{r(1-r)/K}$
Median-based		
Median bias	$\text{Mdn}(B) - \beta$	—
Relative median bias	$[\text{Mdn}(B) - \beta]/\beta$	—
MAD	$1.4826 \times \text{Mdn}(B_k - \text{Mdn}(B))$	—

Performance measure	Empirical calculation	MCSE
Median RMSE	$\sqrt{\text{Bias}_{\text{Mdn}}^2 + \text{MAD}^2}$	—

Note. B_k is the estimate of parameter β from replication k (of K); \bar{B} and S_B are the mean and standard deviation (SD) of the estimates and S_B^2 their variance; \overline{SE} is the mean estimated standard error and \widehat{SE}_k the standard error in replication k ; L_k, U_k are the confidence-interval endpoints, with mean width $\bar{U} - \bar{L}$ and width variance S_W^2 ; c and r are the coverage and rejection rates; $\text{Mdn}(\cdot)$ is the median and MAD the median absolute deviation. A subscript (j) denotes the delete-one (jackknife) replicate computed with replication j removed; for the variance-estimator MCSE, $\bar{v}_{(j)} = (K\bar{v} - \widehat{SE}_j^2)/(K - 1)$ with $\bar{v} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_k \widehat{SE}_k^2$, $S_{B,(j)}^2$ is the leave-one-out variance of the estimates, and relVarBias is the full-sample relative bias of the variance estimator. A dash denotes that no MCSE is computed. Percent-relative forms multiply the corresponding relative measure by 100%.

How will Monte Carlo uncertainty of the estimated performance measures be calculated and reported?

Answer: With the per-measure MCSEs provided by the {simhelpers} package, as given in the table above: closed-form analytic expressions for bias, relative bias, coverage, average width, and the rejection rate, and delete-one jackknife MCSEs for RMSE, relative RMSE, and the relative bias of the variance estimator. They are reported alongside every mean-based performance measure and shown as ± 1 MCSE error bars in the figures. The median-based metrics are reported without MCSEs.

How many simulation repetitions will be used for each condition?

Answer: 1000 replications per condition. Chosen so that MCSEs are small enough to resolve coverage and Type I / power differences, while remaining feasible across 1080 conditions \times 3 methods.

How will missing values due to non-convergence or other reasons be handled?

Answer: We separate three issues, which we handle differently.

Non-convergence. For a given method, a replication is non-converged when the point estimates, standard errors, or confidence intervals for the parameters of interest are not produced or contain undefined or infinite values (this includes fits that raise an error). Following Lonati et al. (2024), such a replication is excluded across all methods, since it flags a challenging case for every estimator; no imputation is used. We report convergence rates per condition and method (Pawel et al., 2026).

Inadmissible (implausible) solutions. A fit may converge yet return an improper solution, for example a negative variance in the measurement-error covariance matrix (Θ) or a non-positive-definite latent disturbance covariance matrix (Ψ) (Dhaene & Rosseel, 2023). Following the previous simulation study conducted, we flag and report these but may retain them in the main analysis, and additionally report a sensitivity check that excludes them. This latter case only if we notice large differences.

Outliers. On the replications where all methods converged, we flag outliers per condition, method, and parameter using interquartile-range (IQR) box-plot at ± 3 IQR on the estimates. If any method-parameter combination flags a replication, it is dropped across all methods within the condition.

Last, rare failures in the copula-based data generation are retried up to five times. Per-condition non-convergence, inadmissibility, and outlier counts are stored.

How do you plan on interpreting the performance measures? (optional)

Answer: Acceptable regions: relative bias within ± 0.10 , coverage within $[0.925, 0.975]$, SE/SD ratio within $[0.90, 1.10]$, Type I error within $[0.025, 0.075]$ (around the nominal 0.05); power is referenced to 0.80. Differences between methods are judged relative to ± 1 MCSE.

Other

Which statistical software/packages do you plan to use?

Answer: R (R Core Team, 2025). Model fitting uses the {lavaan} package (Rosseel, 2012) (the development version) and the {modsem} package (Slupphaug et al., 2024) (also the development version). Non-normal data are generated with the {covsim} (Grønneberg et al., 2022) and {rvinecopulib} (Nagler & Vatter, 2025) packages, MCSEs with the {simhelpers} package (Joshi & Pustejovsky, 2025), and post-processing and figures with the {dplyr} and {ggplot2} packages. Random numbers use L'Ecuyer's combined multiple-recursive generator with a fixed master seed. Note that the plan is to avoid using extra packages for the streams and parallel processing (i.e., {doRNG}, {parallel}), but this may be needed depending on the personal skills of the first author.

Which computational environment do you plan to use?

Answer: The simulation will run on a Mac Studio (Apple M4 Max, 14 cores, 36 GB RAM). The full software stack will be pinned through a Nix environment with the R package {rix} (Rodrigues & Baumann, 2025) built from a dated snapshot of the nixpkgs package collection. The specific versions for R and respective packages will be available in the GitHub repository.

Which other steps will you undertake to make simulation results reproducible? (*optional*)

Answer: A fully pinned Nix environment. With respect to the simulation runs, we have a fixed master seed with independent random-number substreams per parallel worker (which are stored for later access to a specific replication run). We will also share the manuscript files (i.e., qmd), code, and results from the simulation runs in the GitHub repository.

Is there anything else you want to preregister? (*optional*)

Answer: (i) The project title may change, (ii) Simulation run should take about 5/6 days in the specified operating system, and (iii) code for the analyses of the results is currently being written based on the simulation run with 10 replications.

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